

the value of the product ' αn_a ' due to a change in ' n_a ' may be ruled out. Thus, it can be safely concluded that it is ' α ' which is decreasing. ' α ', the transfer coefficient signifies¹³ the fraction of the applied voltage which favours the cathodic reaction, $Zn^{2+} + 2e \rightarrow Zn$. A decrease in the value of ' α ' thus implies that the transfer of electron/electrons is made increasingly difficult. In other words the electrode reaction of Zn(II) is rendered increasingly irreversible with increasing percentages of propylene carbonate. The shift in $E_{1/2}$ to more negative potentials and increase in slope values of log plots are also in agreement with the above conclusion.

A decrease in the value of $k_{f,h}^0$ with increasing percentages of propylene carbonate lends support to the conclusion arrived at on the basis of ' αn_a ' values.

Acknowledgment

Thanks are due to the Principal, Agra College, Agra for the facilities.

References

1. R. PAYNE and I. E. THEODORON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, 76, 2892.
2. R. TAKAHASHI, *Talanta*, 1965, 12, 1211.
3. J. KOUTECKY, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, 47, 323; *Colln. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1953, 18, 597.
4. J. KOUTECKY and J. CEZEK, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1956, 21, 836.
5. J. HEYROVSKY and J. KUTA, "Principles of Polarography", Academic Press, New York, 1966, p, 299.
6. J. N. GAUR, D. S. JAIN and A. KUMAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 165.
7. P. S. VERMA, D. S. JAIN and J. N. GAUR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 586.
8. P. DELAHAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1430.
9. H. MATSUDA and Y. AYABE, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1959, 63, 1164.
10. J. KORYTA, *Electrochim Acta*, 1962, 6, 67.
11. P. J. GELLINGS *Z. Elektrochem., Ber., Busenges, Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 477, 481, 799; 1963, 67, 167.
12. R. GOTO and I. TACHI, *Proc. Intern. Polarogr. Congr.*, 1951, Vol. I, p. 69.
13. P. DELAHAY, 'New Instrumental Methods in Electrochemistry', Interscience Publ., New York, 1954, p, 33.

Standard Heat of Formation of Thorium Tetraacetate†

LAMBODAR THAKUR,* A.K. THAKUR, R. PRASAD and M. F. AHMAD

Post-Graduate Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007 (INDIA)

Manuscript received 10 October 1979, accepted 30 December 1979

WE report in this work the heats of solution of crystalline thorium tetraacetate, $ThAc_4(c)$, and pure acetic acid, $HAc(Ac=CH_3COO)$ in

1M- and 6M-HCl solutions respectively at 298K. The standard heat of formation of $ThAc_4(c)$ can be evaluated by considering the following thermochemical reactions :

As the ionization constant of acetic acid is of the order of 10^{-5} , it would dissolve in HCl solution without ionization as shown in Eq.(2).

From the above equations, we find

$$\Delta H_f^\circ ThAc_4(c) = -(\Delta H_1 - 4\Delta H_2) + \Delta H_f^\circ Th^{4+}(\text{in } x \text{ M-HCl}) + 4\Delta H_f^\circ HAc(l) \quad (4)$$

and

$$\Delta H_f^\circ ThAc_4(c) = -(\Delta H_1 - 4\Delta H_2 - \Delta H_3) + \Delta H_f^\circ ThCl_4(c) + \Delta H_f^\circ HAc(l) - 4\Delta H_f^\circ HCl(\text{in } x \text{ M-HCl}) \quad (5)$$

Experimental

Thorium tetraacetate was prepared by refluxing a mixture of BDH 'AnalaR' crystalline thorium nitrate pentahydrate, $Th(NO_3)_4 \cdot 5H_2O(c)$, with a 2 : 1 mixture of glacial acetic acid and acetic anhydride for several hours¹. A white crystalline solid separated which was washed several times with glacial acetic acid in a fritted-glass filter stick. The final product was vacuum dried at 60° for several hours until there was no loss in weight of the sample. It was analysed for thorium (Found : Th, 49.3 ; Calc. for $ThAc_4(c)$: Th, 49.6%). 'AnalaR' glacial acetic acid was triply distilled under reduced pressure before use.

TABLE 1—HEATS OF SOLUTION OF THORIUM TETRAACETATE AND ACETIC ACID IN 175 ML AQUEOUS HYDROCHLORIC ACID AT 298K IN KJ MOL⁻¹.

Solvents	Compounds	Weight (gms.)	Concn. (mole/l)	ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Mean
1M-HCl	$ThAc_4(c)$	0.25076	0.00306	-45.0	-46.1 ± 0.2
		0.35125	0.00429	-46.5	
		0.38148	0.00466	-46.0	
6M-HCl	$ThAc_4(c)$	0.14216	0.00173	-36.0	-35.7 ± 0.5
		0.17867	0.00218	-35.8	
		0.19078	0.00232	-35.2	
1M-HCl	HAc(l)	1.5500	0.148	-0.80	-0.80
		1.6671	0.159	-0.80	
		1.8631	0.177	-0.80	
6M-HCl	HAc(l)	1.6903	0.161	-0.5	-0.5
		1.9236	0.183	-0.5	
		2.3759	0.226	-0.6	

A closed-system calorimeter described earlier was

† Paper presented at the Annual convention of Chemists. Kurukshetra, Sept. 23-26, 1979.

used². The temperature sensor was a 10k Ω -thermistor and the calorimeter was calibrated electrically with the help of a manganin heater.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the heats of solution values. The average values for ΔH_1 in 1M- and 6M-HCl respectively are -46.1 ± 0.2 and -35.7 ± 0.5 kJ mol⁻¹. The average values for ΔH_2 in the corresponding acid solutions are -0.5 and -0.8 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The heat of solution of ThCl₄(c) in 1M- and 6M-HCl reported previously³ are -241.8 ± 0.7 and -188.3 ± 0.4 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively and ΔH_f° ThCl₄(c) also known from this latter source is -1184.4 ± 1.0 kJ mol⁻¹. The differential heat of formation of hydrochloric acid in 1M-HCl and 6M-HCl solutions are -164.4 ± 0.1 and -153.4 ± 0.2 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively³. The standard heat of formation of Th⁴⁺ in 1M- and 6M-HCl respectively are -768.6 ± 1.7 and -759.0 ± 0.8 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively³. From Cox and Pilcher⁴, ΔH_f° HAc(l) = -484.5 ± 2.0 kJ mol⁻¹. Substituting the above values in Eqs.(4) and (5), we get ΔH_f° ThAc₄(c) = -2662 ± 5 and -2665 ± 5 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The mean of the two values gives ΔH_f° ThAc₄(c) = -2663 ± 5 kJ mol⁻¹.

References

1. R. N. KAPOOR, K. C. PANDE and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 35, 157.
2. L. THAKUR, M. F. AHMAD and R. PRASAD, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, 16A, 661.
3. J. FUGER and D. BROWN, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton*, 1973, 428.
4. J. D. COX and G. PILCHER, *Thermochemistry of Organic and Organometallic Compounds*, Academic Press, New York, 1970, p. 223.

Mössbauer Spectra of Tl(III) hexacyanoferrate(III)

D. KISHORE, G. P. GUPTA, K. C. LAL
Department of Physics, Lucknow University, Lucknow
and

T.N. SRIVASTAVA
Department of Chemistry,
Lucknow University Lucknow.
(U.P.) India

Manuscript received 23 May 1979, accepted 19 November 1979

THE C \equiv N ligand very often gives rise to linkage isomerism yielding C bonded and N bonded metal complexes. Allen and Bonnet¹ observed that in samples of prussian blue containing various interstitial cations the flipping of CN ligand or

exchange of cations occurs around 250°. The phenomenon of cyanide linkage isomerism has also been investigated in iron(III) hexacyanochromate (III)² in which chromium(III) is associated with the C end of the ligands but even at room temperature the nature of bonding is found to change spontaneously yielding Fe(II) bonded through C holes and Cr(III) through N-holes. The identical structure of prussian blue and turnbull's blue³ has been explained on the basis of valence oscillation resonance between two structures in which the charge transfer from Fe³⁺ (high spin) to Fe²⁺ (low spin) or flipping of C \equiv N ligand occurs at the instant of combination.

In order to explore the phenomenon of linkage isomerism in double metal cyanide, we choose to examine the Mössbauer Spectra of a complex of iron(III) with Tl(III) where there is least possibility of electron transfer from one metal to the other. The results are reported in this short communication.

Experimental

Thallium(III) hexacyanoferrate (III) was prepared by double decomposition between Thallium(III) perchlorate and potassium ferricyanide. The hot concentrated solutions of the two reactants were mixed and heated to boiling. The dark blue precipitate was separated, washed several times with water, ethanol and finally with ether. The sample was dried in vacuum and its composition Tl [Fe(CN)₆] was established through elemental analysis. The I. R. spectrum of the sample was recorded in K Br between 4000 to 650 cm⁻¹ using Perkin-Elmer Spectrometer model-337 and a strong peak at 2100 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν C \equiv N is observed.

The Mössbauer spectra were recorded at room and liquid air temperatures on a spectrometer employing proportional counter, a single channel analyser and mechanical drive using constant velocity cams. The source used was Co⁵⁷ in Cu matrix.

Results and Discussion

The observed experimental results are summarized below :-

Chemical shift $\delta = +0.68$ mm/sec. (NP)

Quadrupole splitting $\Delta = 1.20$ mm/sec.

The Δ is almost temperature independent and the Mössbauer fraction is low at room temperature, as shown in the figure 1.

The observed chemical shift in the complex is around that reported for the highly ionic FeCl₃ and FeF₃. The value therefore suggests that Fe(III) in our complex is at least partly high spin which is improbable if the Fe is completely in the C-holes.